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THE HISTORY OF THE CREATION OF NEW VARIETIES AND REFORMS IN THE FIELD OF VEGETABLE GROWING

Hasanova Nishona Normurotovna

Doctoral student of Bukhara State University

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Annotation. *This article describes today's reforms in the field of vegetable growing, which is one of the main branches of agriculture, the creation of new varieties of vegetables, and the history of vegetables. Also, information about the important aspects of the cultivation of vegetables and pulse crops and the history of their creation is highlighted.*

Key words: *gardening, credit, export, import, vegetable growing, greenhouse, local selection, potato growing.*

Аннотация. *В данной статье описаны современные реформы в области овощеводства, которое является одной из основных отраслей сельского хозяйства, создание новых сортов овощей, а также история овощей. Также освещены сведения о важных аспектах выращивания овощей и бобовых культур и истории их создания.*

Ключевые слова: *садоводство, кредит, экспорт, импорт, овощеводство, теплица, местная селекция, картофелеводство.*

Annatatsiya: *Ushbu maqolada dehqonchilikning asosiy tarmoqlaridan bo'lgan sabzavotchilik sohasidagi bugungi kundagi islohotlar, yangi sabzavot navlarining yaratilishi, sabzavotlarning tarixi bayon etilgan. Shuningdek, sabzavot, poliz ekinlarini yetishtirishdagi muhim jihatlar va ularni yaratilish tarixi haqidagi ma'lumotlar yoritib berilgan.*

Tayanch atamalar: *sabzavotchilik, issiqxona, mahalliy seleksiya, kartoshkachilik, dehqonchilik, kredit, eksport, import.*

INTRODUCTION. Vegetable farming is a branch of agriculture that deals with the cultivation of vegetable crops. Vegetable farming is different from other branches of agriculture, in particular, crops are grown in open and protected (closed) lands, most crops are grown in one season. Vegetable crops are grown in open fields (in spring, summer and autumn), vegetables and seeds, and vegetables are grown in closed areas. The large number of types of crops grown in horticulture is distinguished by the diversity of their biological properties. About 70 types of vegetable crops are grown in Uzbekistan and occupy an important place in agriculture.

ANALYSIS AND METHODS. It is known that the existing natural climatic conditions in the country allow for sustainable development of agricultural products, especially fruit and vegetable growing. The President and the government of the Republic of Uzbekistan are paying great attention to the development of fruit and vegetables as a priority direction in the process of transitioning the industry to market relations. After all, the fact that a significant part of the foreign currency income of the country is formed due to the sale of fruit and vegetable products to foreign markets also indicates the priority of radical reform and rapid development of the sector. In particular, a number of decisions and decrees have been adopted in recent years. These include PF-5388 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated March 29, 2019 "On additional measures for the rapid development of fruit and vegetable production in the Republic of Uzbekistan" and "Uzbekistan" dated October 23, 2019 Decree No. PF-5853 "On confirmation of the strategy of agricultural development of the Republic for 2020-2030" and additional measures to increase the efficiency of the export of fruit and vegetable products to foreign markets dated October 17, 2018 PQ-3978, PQ-4239 of March 14, 2019 "On measures for the development of agricultural cooperation in the field of fruit and vegetables" can be cited. Today, more than 80 types of agricultural products grown in our republic are exported to 71 countries of the world. Uzbekistan ranks 3rd in the world in the cultivation of carrots, 7th in the cultivation of cucumbers, 8th in the cultivation of cherries and figs.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS. As a result of scientific research conducted at the scientific research institute of horticulture, viticulture and winemaking, 3 new varieties of strawberry were created. Uzbek scientists have created 3 new varieties of strawberries that are resistant to hot summer days. These varieties are intended for growing in the greenhouse and in the open field. They produce for 5-6 months of the year. The "Dildor" variety, which is resistant to hot summer days, the "Kamola" and "Dilnoz" varieties, which produce once in the open field throughout the year, were created by local selection. With this, the cultivation of seedlings of these varieties is

started. Currently, there are "Uzbekistanskaya", "Culver", "Tashkentskaya", "Zengazengana" varieties of strawberries. "Miss Uzbekistan" in 2014, "Beautiful", "Redgauntel", "Cobra" introduced in 2018, and "Medvey" in 2020 were included in the state register. In the regions of Tashkent, Namangan, Andijan and Samarkand, strawberry plantations are widely established and their areas are expanding. Also, the employees of the institute prepare sukat (candied fruit) from peaches, plums, lemons, golden currants for public consumption and recommendations to farmers. According to information, the homeland of this fruit is France. Cultivated strawberries began to be grown in Uzbekistan at the end of the 19th century and the beginning of the 20th century [5].

Breeding scientists of the Scientific Research Institute of Vegetable Crops and Potatoes under the Ministry of Agriculture invented the early potato variety "Tashkent Tale" suitable for the soil and climatic conditions of the country. Authors of this variety are Rustam Nizomov, Jasur Rahmatullayev, Muhammadjon Rasulov and Dilshod Tursunov. The new variety was patented by the Intellectual Property Agency in 2023. Foreign potato varieties such as "Surya", "Spunta", "Ranomi", "Passion", "Louisiana", "Orea" and "Constance" are used by farmers and agricultural enterprises for the 2022 harvest in Uzbekistan. cultivated. About 152 varieties of potatoes are included in the State Register of Agricultural Crops recommended for planting in the territory of Uzbekistan, of which 19 varieties were created by scientists of local scientific research institutes. Taking into account the soil and climate conditions, potatoes are grown on an area of 71,000 hectares in 40 specialized potato-growing districts of Uzbekistan. 23 of them are used for growing seed potatoes, and "Super-elita" and "Elita" seeds are grown in 39 regions of 9 districts.

Among the vegetable crops, carrots are distinguished by their ease of cultivation and their usefulness. That is why it is sown in many areas of our republic and a good harvest is obtained. It is one of the oldest known root vegetables. This type of vegetable was first eaten in Afghanistan, where it grew wild 4000 years ago. Carrots were originally purple and 400 years ago they were artificially brought to the orange color we know. Red carrots first appeared in the Netherlands and were eaten only by the royal family. Several varieties of carrots were created in the Middle Ages. In particular, in the 17th century, one of the best varieties of carrot "Karotel" was obtained.

Today, 29 varieties of carrots are grown in all regions of our country. These include "Amsterdam", "Lenochka", "Beloved", "Shante 2461", "Golden Autumn", "Emperor", "Canada" and for winter storage "Vitamin B-6", "Geranda", "Thursday", "Moscow" ", "Forto", "Aristo" and many other types are being cultivated [1].

Cabbage is one of the most popular vegetables. It occupies a leading place in the cuisine of many nations. The word cabbage comes from the ancient Greek word "kaputum" (head), which refers to the specific shape of the vegetable. Cabbage has been present in the cuisine of the peoples living around the Mediterranean basin since ancient times. Therefore, the homeland of cabbage is considered to be the shores of this sea. Ibn Sina's book "The Laws of Medicine" also extensively covered the healing properties of cabbage, through which Europeans in the Middle Ages promoted cabbage a lot as a medicinal food. Today, such types of cabbage as white cabbage, cauliflower, red cabbage, broccoli, kohlrabi, Beijing cabbage, and Chinese cabbage are grown in the territory of our republic. 132 varieties of cabbage are recommended for planting in the republic and included in the State Register of Agriculture. In particular, white cabbage "Akbosh", "Adema F1", "Bourbon F1", "Lyunskaya", "Navroz", cauliflower "Kashmer F1", "Barcelona F1", "Talassa F1", broccoli "Agassi F1", "Ironman F1", "Marathon F1" and other varieties are grown.

As we mentioned above, Uzbekistan ranks 7th in the world in terms of cucumber production. Cucumber is an annual herb. There is information that cucumbers were cultivated 3 thousand years ago. Its homeland is India, and it is now cultivated in many countries of the world. It still grows naturally in the tropical and subtropical regions of India, on the slopes of the Himalayas. It spread from India to Greece and Italy and later entered China. It was introduced to other parts of Europe by the Romans. Cucumber entered France in the 9th century, England in the 14th century, and North America in the middle of the 16th century. There is an assumption that cucumbers entered Russia from East Asian countries in the 16th century. But according to the opinion of some historians, cucumber was known to Russian lands in the 9th century. Ecuador is the largest producer of cucumbers. For the first time, a greenhouse that allows growing cucumbers all year round was specially created in ancient Rome for Empress Fiberia. Because the emperor liked to eat cucumbers every day. A monument to cucumbers has been erected in the Russian city of Nezhin. Every year, July 27 is celebrated worldwide as International Cucumber Day. Today, in our country, mainly F1 productive hybrid varieties, "Gulnoz", "Parad", "Konkurent", "Navroz", "F1 Alibi", "F1 Ajax", "Orzu" varieties of cucumbers are grown. "F1 Alibi" and "F 1 Ajax" are Dutch hybrids, entered into the state register in 2001. It is intended for preserves and salads. In addition, there are dozens of varieties such as "Benefit F1", "Alekseyevich F1", "Baby with a finger", "Emelya F1", "Droplet", "Elegant", "Aelita", "Agat", "Movir 1" [2].

Tomato is one of the leading vegetable crops in our country. According to the data of 2014, the total cultivated area of this crop is about 75.4 thousand hectares, the

harvest is 1.6-1.7 million tons, or the annual harvest per hectare is 21.2-22 It corresponded to .5 tons. In 2012-2014, promising, transportable new tomato varieties were tested. The varieties "Asiyo", "Sovga", "MJ-7" were used as objects of research. The comparative variety "Surkhan 142", the highest total yield was observed in "Sovga" and "Asia" varieties.

If we talk about the history of this vegetable, the homeland of tomato is the territories of the countries of Peru, Ecuador and Chile of the South American continent. It was first cultivated in Mexico. It was brought to Europe by European traders, first to Spain, Portugal, then to Italy, France and other countries. Tomato is considered a poisonous plant and grown by gardeners only as a decorative plant. In the middle of the 18th century, it was widely cultivated in Russia. Tomatoes entered Central Asia, including Uzbekistan, through Russia.

Scientists of the Scientific Research Institute of Vegetable Crops and Potatoes under the Ministry of Agriculture conducted research on the cultivation of tomato varieties suitable for the soil and climate conditions of this region in Bukhara region [4]. The Ministry provided information about the results achieved in the pilot testing processes. It is reported that such varieties as "Bobkant F1", "Tomsk F1", "Lojain F1", "Red stone", "Seraj F1", "Independence 28", "Rio Grande" successfully passed the hot weather conditions of July. the experiment shows good indicators in the process of testing. Scientists of the institute say that tomato, which is the main vegetable crop, is a cold-loving plant, so it stops growing and developing when the air temperature exceeds +40 degrees.

CONCLUSION. It should be noted that due to strong heat, some parts of the tomato fruit get sunstroke and the flowers fall off. This leads to a decrease in the quality of tomatoes. This year, the air temperature in some parts of Bukhara region, especially in Zhondar district, was +47 degrees, which required special attention for tomatoes. For the purpose of shading, a 5 cm thick layer of dried corn stalks and straw-like plants was laid over the tomatoes.

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